

What if our cell brain is a space travelling- compass

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Abstract

The disciplinary diversity connection between astronomy and neuroscience and that's obvious in every cell brain can contain a signal of our outer space. Can ether of space determine our future of health care insurance? There are many types of astronomical affective field in our brain. This paper gathered the theories and methods which discuss the vantage point of surreal space with Copernican Revolution in neuroscience that mapped a plot paralyzed with the earth and the universe. The learning in the planetarium environment it will affect in us or draw a pattern of thoughts. There are many questions will be asked what if a solar-terrestrial interaction causes a dangerous disease? Is there relationship between radio signals from space and brain thoughts? How could Cosmological Origin facilitate the collapse of wave functions within the brain space?

Keywords: astronomy, neuroscience, brain, Copernican revolution, earth, universe, solar terrestrial interactions, disease, radio signals, cosmological origin

1. Introduction

According to the artist, a fundamental principle of Cogito is that space exploration is about more than only the "outer unknown," but also about "exploring ourselves in this bigger dimension that is also part of us." «We» (de Paulis 2018a). She mentions three major influences that came together in the project: the «Dualistic Problem in Contemporary Cosmology, » Frank White's The Overview

(1)Wikipedia Contributors. Mind–body problem. Source Wikipedia.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mind%E2%80%93body_problem

Effect, and Solaris De Paulis refers to the following issue as the "Dualistic Problem":

«As cosmology advances in its understanding of the world, the role of the mind in interpreting the picture of 'reality' remains largely unknown» (de Paulis 2019, 199). The existential consequences of addressing enormous scales.

Since humans cannot have direct sensory experience with the universe, this remains an unresolved topic. That question is used by the artist to make the leap into virtual space travel: «Radio waves allow us to travel with our ideas for farther and quicker than our senses, into a realm of abstract cosmic spaces»

(2)ExoMars orbiter core module completed. www.esa.int. source
https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Space_Science/ExoM

ars_orbiter_core_module_completed.

In turn, White coined the phrase "Overview Effect" in the 1980s.

2-Cogito exploration (1): - He uses it to describe "the cognitive shift that occurs in the minds of astronauts after seeing the Earth from outer space. White became a consultant and partner, and de Paulis uses his concept to investigate how "the way we understand Earth is extremely subjective."

The artist chose Solaris as the first fictional reference of someone transmitting brain activity to a planet and experiencing a complicated psychological experience as a result.

Given the scope of inspirations and ideas, the project required some boundaries.

(3)NASA SETI (Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence) Microwave Observing Project

https://public.nrao.edu/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/VLA_5d4_Clouds-1170x600.jpg

The First: - de Paulis distanced himself from space outreach. According to her, motivation was not to be an advocate, but to raise concerns about the appropriateness of humans for space travel.

The Second: - despite her involvement with the Search for Extraterrestrial Life (SETI) community, she distanced herself from them in this endeavor.

In this distancing, two positions are at risk.

A first is a critique of SETI's rational and mathematical picture of people, and a shift towards a more complicated and conflicting portrayal.

A second position likewise required a technical choice during the design phase. There is debate within SETI and METI (Messaging Extraterrestrial Intelligence) regarding transmitting messages to aliens. Signals since doing so risks being detected. As a result, the researchers decided against targeting a specific celestial object in the transmission of brain waves. They agreed to keep the transmitting antenna stationary in order to spread the signal across the sky. Regardless of how unlikely, there is a desire in

Cogito for "a potential extraterrestrial intelligence" to decode and recreate the signal.

A Third, although not rejecting its speculative nature, the endeavor was keen to distinguish itself from "pseudoscience." The knowledge of this feature among the collaborators warrants more examination, because it was critical to their relationship.

3- The Copernicus's view of the universe was altered: -(2)

The universe did include Earth and other planets prior to Copernicus. However, the earth was more than simply another planet among many in the universe. Instead, Earth was thought to be unique in comparison to the other planets and the rest of the

(4)source <https://www.observatoiredeparis.psl.eu/premiere-edition-critique-de.html>

A result, there was a distinct center-periphery divide between earth and non-earth—the earth was thought exceptional, implying a geocentric and thus egocentric perspective of the world, a vantage position from within earth.

The earth's uniqueness was further enhanced by its immobile nature. The earth, as the Centre that binds the entire cosmos together, was not intended to change because any shift would cause the universe to collapse. Thus, the world was imagined in a temporal sense—the earth was supposed to be

eternally present with no change in space or time. Together, the earth was defined by its uniqueness, such as its role as the Centre, and its relationship to the universe, such as a-spatiotemporal vs. spatiotemporal. His successors Kepler, Bruno, Gallilei, and Newton empirically proved his theory.

Provided a distinct vision of earth inside the universe. He attributed the observed movements to the earth. Rather than the sun and all other planets spinning around the earth as the Centre of the cosmos, he proposed that the world revolves around the sun as the Centre of the universe. This resulted in the replacement of the geocentric and egocentric views of the cosmos with a heliocentric and allocentric perspective of the earth-universe relationship.

In the event of a heliocentric framework, the earth loses its uniqueness in terms of position, role, and time Features. The Earth is no longer at the Centre of the cosmos, revolving around which all other planets circle. Instead, the earth is replaced by the sun, and the earth's unique position is therefore lost. Furthermore, it is no longer the planet that keeps the cosmos together, but the sun—the earth's pivotal role in the universe is also lost.

(5) https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/3/33/Geoz_wb_en.svg

Finally, the earth's a-spatiotemporal nature as not subject to change is replaced by attributing movements to the earth as it revolves around the sun—the earth is thus characterized by the same spatiotemporal features as the rest of the universe, albeit to varying degrees, e.g., on a smaller scale. The pre-Copernican view's specialness and dichotomy of earth are replaced by non-specialness of earth and intrinsic earth.

4- The link between the earth and the universe: -
(2)

Copernicus was able to consider the earth's non -

3D Visualization of Phenomenal Consciousness

(7) 3D visualization of phenomenal conscious

specialty and its inherent link with the universe in this way. He abandoned the usual vantage point from within the earth and replaced it with one that allowed him to see what happens outside the world within the universe and how that shapes the earth itself, such as its movements within the universe. Copernicus, like the tourist travelling to the neighboring hill to observe the city and cathedral,

transferred the viewpoint point from within earth to what I call the vantage position from beyond earth.

One could be inclined to argue that we now know better. The premise of mind has been contested in both philosophy and, more recently, neuroscience. There is no longer a mind; mental traits such as consciousness and self are founded on the brain and hence physical or, more accurately, neuronal rather than primarily mental, i.e., non-physical. Monism with materialism/physicalism, panpsychism. Or dual-aspect monism replaces mind-body dualism.

5- The discovery of the neurological basis of mental traits has sparked an investigation into their neuronal mechanisms: -(2)

In the dispute over consciousness, for example has been characterized as the bare minimum of neural mechanisms required for any one conscious percept. Recent advances in consciousness research

the full NCC, which supports conscious experiences in their entirety, regardless of the contents.

(8) 3D visualization of NCC and NCA

The NCC takes on unique neuronal characteristics within the brain. These distinct but not fully understood neural properties are thought to underpin

Consciousness, distinguishing them from others.

The NCA Neuronal characteristics that only serve to mediate unconsciousness. Thus, the NCC represent a unique neuronal role for consciousness and imply a neuronal dichotomy of consciousness vs. unconsciousness. Thus, specialization and dichotomy are now "placed" within the brain itself, in terms of two sets of neuronal properties and mechanisms. Without going into detail, these specific neuronal mechanisms include, to name a few, information integration, recurrent processing, access to global workspace embodiment higher order cognition, predictive error, or minimization, temporo-spatial dynamics.

How can we consider the uniqueness of neural mechanisms of mental traits and their distinction from those of other organs?

Of non-mental characteristics? Only from within the brain itself, and more precisely from within the

3D Visualization of NCC and NCA in Phenomenal Consciousness

(6)File: Consciousness phenomenal-functional (en).png - Wikiversity.commons.wikimedia.org. source [https://en.m.wikiversity.org/wiki/File:Consciousness_phenomenal-functional_\(en\).png](https://en.m.wikiversity.org/wiki/File:Consciousness_phenomenal-functional_(en).png) have introduced two refined interpretations of the NCC as follows: (1) the content-specific NCC, which determines a specific phenomenal distinction with an experience; and (2)

neural circuits presumably underpinning mental qualities, is this conceivable. In neuroscience, a "vantage position from within the brain" is thus assumed. Thus, in neuroscience, a neuro-centric view of mental traits replaces the mento-centric view of psychology. Despite the difference between mentocentric and neurocentric views of mental features, both psychology/cognitive science and neuroscience still assume a rather egocentric vantage point, i.e., from within either mind or brain, which entails what I refer to as brain-world relation further down. Both approaches to mental traits are thus pre-Copernican.

Some approaches may argue that they are not neurocentric since their basic substrate of mental qualities such as awareness is thought to be information cognition or the body. True, these methods are no longer neuro-centric. However, this does not absolve them of their egocentric nature. The ego-centric approach has now been translated from the brain to the body, cognition, or

information—they are thus body-centric, information-centric, and cognition-centric, and are thus distinguished by "vantage points from within information, cognition, or body." As with neuro-centric methods, the specialization of mental features and their dichotomy with non-mental features are still preserved in these systems,

indicating that they are pre-Copernican.

6- The Origin of 10^{20} Joules in the Universe

When the volume of the universe for the bound is 10^{20} J, the significance of 10^{20} J as a fundamental quantum arises.

In comparison to the present, boundary situation is accommodated. The following parameters are visible in the current universe: age: $4.2 \cdot 10^{17}$ seconds, $r = 1.26 \cdot 10^{26}$ m, m , cross sectional area (πr^2) = $4.99 \cdot 10^{52}$ m², $8.38 \cdot 10^{78}$ m³. The boundary condition is derived from:

- 1) G (Newtonian G and mass density), where G is the Newtonian Gravitational Constant and $\rho = 1.67 \cdot 10^{-27}$ kg/m³, corresponding to one proton per cubic meter. According to the open cold matter (OCMD) model given by Hoffman et al. the resulting squared frequency is equivalent to an age of $3.0 \cdot 10^{18}$ seconds (90 billion years) and is within range of the fate (final epoch) of the universe. The final boundary parameters are $r = 8.99 \cdot 10^{26}$ m, cross sectional area = $2.54 \cdot 10^{54}$ m², and volume = $3.04 \cdot 10^{81}$ m³.

3D Visualization of Solar Activity and Mortality Rate

(10) 3D visualization of solar activity and morality rate

The interpretation of the cyclicity associated with cerebrovascular disease mortality as being dependent on changes in have shown a strong convergence on universal limitations. However, for the current solar-terrestrial model of Cosmo epidemiology, we began by isolating the temporal component.

7- DIMENSIONAL Examination OF A SOLAR-TERRESTRIAL CIRCUIT

(9) Shape of the universe. Source Wikipedia.<https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shape> The translation of the cyclicity related with cerebrovascular illness mortality as unexpected upon variances in β have checked merging upon all-inclusive limitations. For the current solar-terrestrial demonstrate of Cosmo epidemiology, in any case, we started by segregating the worldly delay between nearby Helio physical vacillations and the impact that they have on geophysical changes ~ 14.60 a long time afterward. Attractive hesitance inside an attractive circuit is analogous to resistance inside an electrical circuit. For the current show, we hypothesized that the Earth and Sun are associated attractive circuits bounded by their physical and spatial impediments. The hesitance of an attractive circuit can be calculated utilizing the equation:

$$R = L / (\mu' \mu_r \cdot m^2)$$

Where R = hesitance (**turns / Ωs**), L = length of the circuit (m), μ = penetrability of free space, μ_r == relative porousness, and m^2 = surface zone between circuits. We expected that the length between the circuits is the inexact separate between the Earth and Sun ($\sim 1.496 \cdot 10^{11}$ m), the penetrability of free space is $1.256 \cdot 10^{-6}$ m ·

$\text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$, the relative penetrability for complimentary space is 1, and the zone would be characterized as a circle with outspread units rise to the separate between the Earth and Sun. The result of the calculation would be $4.24 \cdot 10^{-7}$ To get a recurrence, we duplicated this esteem by the wave impedance of free space ($3.7 - 10^2 \Omega$). The (11) 3D visualization of solar terrestrial magnetic circuit resultant worldly consistent for the hesitance of the Sun-Earth attractive circuit would be ($1.568 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ Hz}$). Given the known recurrence related with a single turn, we assist calculated the remove that each turn (i.e., overlay) within the Earth-Sun circuit would contain in arrange to suit the 14.60-year cyclicity. The proportionate term of 14.60 a long time in seconds would be $4.60 \cdot 10^8 \text{ s}$ given the normal year length of 365 days. The division of the cycle term by the recurrence related with a single turn would result in around $7.21 \cdot 10^4$ turns or folds within the attractive flux isolating the Earth and Sun.

is $2.07 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}$, which is within the arrange of size of a Soil span, and whose coefficient varies as it were by a figure of around π , the characteristic geometric change for a circular boundary. This may be conceptualized as wave-pockets or mutilations within the attractive field lines that interface the earth to the Sun. Allegorically talking, these flux lines would be hubs upon which Helio physical annoyances vibrate and transmit designs of lively movement to the Earth over long periods of time. This handle would require that the constrain of transmission speed be much shorter than the speed of light. In any case, this balance in transmission must still comply widespread imperatives. The engendering speed between the Earth and Sun along the attractive flux folds can be calculated agreeing to:

$$v=d/t$$

Where v = speed, d = distance (m), and t = time (s). Hence, for a separate of $1.496 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ m}$, and a time of $4.6 \cdot 10^8 \text{ s}$, the relative proliferation speed would be $3.25 \cdot 10^2 \text{ m}^{-1}$ or the surmised speed of sound. This may recommend that the engendering along the attractive flux folds can be seen as a weight wave. From this, we may be able to discover a weight equivalent of this prepare.

Given that the matter thickness of space is around $10^{-27} \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, which the circular remove between the Sun and Soil is within the arrange of 10^{33} m^3 , the mass proportionality of the space between these two objects would be 10^6 kg . Active vitality can be investigated as we are portraying a moving wave, characterized by:

$$E = 1/2Mv^2$$

8- Conclusion

In this paper we have discussed a lot of scenarios like Cogito is that space exploration is about more than only the "outer unknown," but also about "exploring ourselves in this bigger dimension that is

3D Visualization of Solar-Terrestrial Magnetic Circuit

Energy = 1.77e+11 J

The normal distance involved by a crease would be the remainder of the distance between the Earth and Sun and the number of turns. The distance a single overlay involves between the Earth and Sun

also a part of us." The Copernicus's view of the universe was altered. We know the difference between SETI and METI (Messaging Extraterrestrial Intelligence) regarding transmitting messages to aliens.

We display the definitions about NCC and NCA. And how that works in the neural way, in addition to provide the theories and laws and connect it with neuroscience and Astronomy. Firstly, The Origin of 10^{20} Joules in the Universe. DIMENSIONAL Examination OF A SOLAR-TERRESTRIAL CIRCUIT.

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